

D7.3 – Interim Dissemination and Communication Plan and Report 2

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the interim Dissemination and Communication Plan and Report 2 for the ARIADNEplus project. The report covers the second 18-month period (M18-M36, i.e. July 2020-December 2021) for the dissemination and communication activities undertaken by the lead team at PIN Scrl and all the (40+) partners who are involved in the project. The figures used actually go through M35 due to the holidays falling at the end of the deadline, so this report has been prepared a month early to allow for review and submission.

The first Dissemination and Communication Plan identified the different stakeholders and described how these may be reached. During the first period, the project partners and their organisations were the main focus for dissemination and communication, with this policy continuing for the second period (M19-M36). Information and news have continued to be published on the website, which is aimed at a wider audience, with other methods of communication which have included partner's mailing lists, social media channels and the Project Newsletter.

There have not been any training events scheduled for period 2 and Transnational Access has remained suspended due to the current travel problems. Most of the activity by the project partners has been focussed upon the ingestion and publication of their datasets which started to appear in the public Portal from April onwards. It was agreed that the best method of dissemination would be national campaigns led by each of the partners who would target their local archaeological communities through their preferred communication channels when their datasets were published, backed up by the Project team via the website and Twitter. The first partner to do this was ADS who conducted a very effective Twitter campaign over a week-long period which also helped provide a template for the partners to use going forward. In each case, an increase in visits to the Portal was observed. Several more of these campaigns will take place during the final reporting period, along with those planned for international dissemination of the project as a whole.

The ARIADNEplus website has met its M36 targets with Twitter and Facebook being major sources of referral along with partner websites and E-RIHS, the Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (who has also been involved in the development of the Application Profile for this sub-domain). The updated Home page design was launched at the start of Period 2 with new content being added in the form of a Training Hub (providing training resources) and also a couple of webinars being made available. The Newsletter has a good opening rate at over 40%, and the subscriber list has grown slowly but steadily. Slideshare and Zenodo have also proven to be effective for promoting the project objectives with the three translations of the Guidelines to "Fairify data management and make data reusable" into Czech, Portuguese and Turkish have generated over 1,000 views and 940 downloads. Twitter continues to be the most effective channel for dissemination.

The Partners have participated in 20 conferences and events, giving presentations and taking part in round tables and workshops including CAA and EAA which were held virtually as were the great majority of events during this time. ARIADNEplus has also produced eleven articles and papers, the most recent drawing on the TNA training completed at the start of 2020 on CIDOC-CRM at PIN.

The Communication and dissemination plan for M37-M48 involves an intensification of activities as well as specific targeting of the sub-domains as more data appears in the Portal, the pilots are published and training materials are prepared for a new section in the Training Hub. CAA and EAA are the two major conferences targeted by the project, along with DH2022 in Japan as this will promote ARIADNEplus in Asia.

2 Introduction and objectives

Work package 7 is responsible for the definition of an overall communication and dissemination strategy and planning for this, along with the co-ordination of training. The main activities undertaken are largely communication about the project and project results to the wide range of identified stakeholders. These communication activities¹ also require the support of the project partners, e.g. using their own media channels to promote the project action. Work package 2 focusses on the more specific activities of networking and integration which involves partners disseminating the results of the project through meetings, workshops, papers and training, for example, to their peers within the research community. Work package 7 in turn supports Work package 2 by advertising the networking and integration activities, making resources available (such as reports).

As the deliverable D2.4 Interim Report on Networking and Integration covers much of the dissemination activity for M19-M36, this deliverable mainly focuses upon the communication activity for the same period and the planning for M37-M48 for future communication and dissemination activities.

As all are aware, the COVID-19 epidemic has had a profound impact on the way we work and communicate since late February 2020 and has made face-to-face meetings and events almost impossible. Nearly all our activities are currently digital and mainly conducted online. Even as we start to return to our more normal lives, we still have to practice social distancing, foreign travel is all but impossible and it seems it will months, if not years, before large social gatherings such as conferences will happen again. The ARIADNEplus community has adapted very well to this seismic change, carrying on their work from home, using Skype and Zoom to meet virtually and have discussions and meetings with their colleagues. Fortunately, the dissemination and communication strategy is largely digital but the current situation has still forced us to reassess how we can be more effective and what we can do to replace the lost in-person dissemination opportunities of major European conferences such as CAA and EAA, which have taken place as virtual events. Training has seen the greatest impact with Transnational Access in-house visits postponed and any final year activities in doubt.

With the current limitations in mind, the dissemination and communication activities have been reorganised. Some activities continue to be postponed or cancelled, mainly those relating to physical events, other new ones have been implemented such as the National Dissemination campaigns when each new dataset is uploaded into the Portal.

¹ Making the Most of Your H2020 Project

Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation - the European IPR Helpdesk

3 Report on Dissemination and Communication M19-M36

3.1 Reaching the stakeholder community

ARIADNEplus has a wide range of stakeholders² who have varying priorities and interests. By developing an understanding of the needs and interests of each group, the project aims to make its dissemination activities more relevant to the people and organisations interested in using the research infrastructure. Awareness of the needs of community helps identify the best channels for contacting stakeholder groups (such as email lists, conferences, other means) and in the design and planning of dissemination materials and activities, thus helping to raise the visibility of the project and promote use of its outputs:

- internal stakeholders in the partner institutions who have an interest or involvement in archaeological research or management responsibilities relating to project activities;
- research institutions active in the field as represented by managers and senior researchers with management duties such as deans, directors etc.;
- scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines and the wider scientific community;
- international networks and research infrastructures in related disciplines;
- policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission;
- cultural Heritage institutions interested in activities such as data management and training;
- commercial organisations such as private companies involved in archaeology, cultural heritage and consultancy;
- semi-professional and amateur organisations and groups;
- media and the public at large.

For the purposes of this report, we will summarise how each of these stakeholders has been addressed by the current strategy and activities and the plans for M37-M48.

To date, the main focus of the project dissemination is on internal stakeholders, keeping them up to date with the various activities going on in the different sub-groups, co-ordinating contributions to workshops and conferences and in turn, relying on them to forward and disseminate information within their own organisations and through their own media/social media channels. Basecamp has, therefore, been used as the main means of communication internally and all partners are signed up to the newsletters, mainly as a reminder to visit the website. Twitter is also widely used among the researchers. Likewise, research institutions are reached in these networks, as subscribers to newsletters and blogs and as followers on Twitter.

During the second period, nearly all events were virtual (or hybrid) which greatly reduces the opportunities for communicating the project activities informally, e.g. through stands, distributing literature and informal chats during breaks. However, the partners have managed to attend a number of these events and organise workshops. The project has now increased by a further 13 Associate Partners in addition to the Heidelberg Academy of Sciences based in Heidelberg, Germany. As well as the work of WP7, dissemination activities form part of the networking and integration activities described in D2.3 Interim Report on Networking and Integration. The most recent of these are reported in D2.4 Interim report on networking and integration.

² Please refer to D7.1 for detailed descriptions of each one of these identified stakeholders.

ARIADNEplus continues to liaise with the SEADDA Cost Action, the two having many members in common. For example, on the 8th September, ARIADNEplus along with the SEADDA Cost Action hosted a session (476) entitled “Understanding and expanding capacity in archaeological data management beyond western Europe” based on *Theme 3: The new normality of heritage management and museums in post-Covid times* at the virtual EAA 2021 Conference. This virtual session attracted around 50 participants. The presentations can be viewed at: <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/ea-2021-ariadneplus-session-476-presentations-available/>.

In terms of communication, the website aims to reach all the stakeholders which also includes the public and third parties. Whilst English is used widely in the research community, this does limit the reach of ARIADNEplus dissemination, so several of the website pages have been translated into other main European Languages (Italian, Greek, English, Slovenian, Czech, Bulgarian, Polish, Hungarian, French, German, Spanish Swedish and Dutch) as well as Japanese to facilitate a wider understanding of the project aims, especially in central and eastern Europe where many of the countries have not been previously involved in ARIADNE. The website statistics (c.f. Section 3.3.2) illustrate the usefulness of these translations.

Resources amongst the consortium and externally

The ARIADNE consortium consists of 41 partners in 27 countries including Belgium, Sweden, Denmark, Norway, Finland, Iceland, United Kingdom, Ireland, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovenia, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Greece, Cyprus, Israel, Croatia, Romania and Bulgaria. From outside of Europe, there are partners from Argentina, the US and Japan. CARARE, as a membership organisation, also includes other countries within its membership such as Lithuania. During the first period, the partners were very active in disseminating news about the project and have continued, albeit with some restrictions, during the second period. Activities have included:

- Creating links to the ARIADNEplus website from the partners’ own site (all partners)
- Giving presentations at national and international events
- Organising ARIADNE workshops at international conferences
- Distributing ARIADNE dissemination materials
- Distributing notices about ARIADNE activities to mailing lists
- Writing articles about ARIADNE activities for in-house newsletters
- Contributing articles to the ARIADNE website
- Contributing articles to local newspapers and television
- Disseminating news and information about ARIADNE via the social networks
- Participating in meetings organized by research infrastructures, projects and international initiatives and giving presentations about ARIADNE and/or distributing materials

For example, there has been regular dissemination of ARIADNE News and Events through CARARE's monthly newsletters and Twitter.

Information and news

The project has communicated information and news about the project’s activities and related areas via the project website, a project newsletter, social media channels and (to a more limited extent) to the press.

In addition, a new ‘Features’ section was added where longer articles on more general topics related to the project and archaeology can be found, these being aimed more at the general public and

interested third parties. Following the first two articles published in period 1, five more articles have been added as follows:

- Why does ARIADNE use the Getty AAT and not Wikidata as its main reference vocabulary?
- First ARIADNEplus Workshop on VRE Use Cases
- ARIADNEplus Progress Update Workshop: The Way Forward
- The 2nd VRE Workshop: Ancient DNA and Environmental Data and Research
- Impact of COVID-19 on Archaeology and Cultural Heritage.

These longer style articles illustrate the topics that the project covers in depth, the approaches used and progress made in contrast to the shorter news items.

Internal communication channels

Two main forms of internal communication are being used within the project at present: Basecamp and D4Science. Basecamp is the main platform used for 'broadcasting' information and requests to all involved (there are now 216 people registered from all the partners, an increase of 32 people since M18), often with links to supporting documentation in the project repository which is held in D4Science. Within Basecamp, there are around 30 sub-groups (for targeted messaging). It appears that posts in Basecamp are continuing to meet the internal communication needs, especially as participants are able to interact and discuss topics of interest.

For those partners who are directly involved in the technical development of the Portal, D4Science is the preferred means of communication. Currently, there are two main VREs, each with their own messaging channel:

- ARIADNEplus_Mappings – this is the environment in which everything concerning mapping strategies and tools happens. From here is also possible to access the 3M and the Vocabulary mapping tools.
- ARIADNEplus_AggregationManagement – this is reserved to the small team in charge of coordinating the aggregation of the partners' metadata.

Mailing lists

Several partners have mailing lists, along with their own social media channels. When the project has an announcement that requires dissemination, the information is posted in Basecamp and the relevant partners will then forward this as appropriate. The most recent example is the request to disseminate the survey on TNA requirements for 2022.

Social networks

The main social network used by the project is Twitter, with a small Facebook presence for key postings. Many of the partners also have Twitter feeds which are used to retweet ARIADNEplus tweets. The project also has membership of a number of archaeology-related LinkedIn groups and these were used to advertise the first TNA call. In addition, ARIADNEplus has continued uploading reports and presentations of wider interest to the Slideshare account established for the original project.

3.2 The ARIADNEplus website

The ARIADNEplus website and Twitter are the two main communication channels for the wider stakeholder community with a presence also on Facebook in order to cover the more popular channels.

The ARIADNEplus website

The ARIADNEplus website (<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>) aims to provide information about the project to all stakeholders and to related projects, and provides a single point of access to the research infrastructure via the Portal. The graphic solution used for the website frontend is based on a responsive design that can adapt to the user's behaviour and environment based on screen size, platform and orientation. Since the launch in February 2019, some minor updates were made to the website with the addition of new content such as the Features section and the translations of the main information pages during the first period, as reported in the previous version of this report (D7.2). At the end of Period 1 and three months into lockdown, it was decided to reorganise the website due to its increasing importance as a communication and dissemination channel with the lack of physical interaction for the foreseeable future. This new design focused on the following four main areas of interest to end users:

- The ARIADNEplus Community – the landing page introduces the project and presents the two leaflets aimed at i) archaeological researchers and ii) professionals and heritage managers respectively, along with iii) a 24-page synopsis of the project and its activities. The sub-sections consist of:
 - Our Network – summary page of all the external organisations and Associate Partners involved in the project and their roles and activities
 - Consortium – short description for each partner (beneficiary) in the project
 - Associate Partners – summary page of all the Associate Partners (14 to date) which shows the name, logo, and locations. The name links to a description for each organisation and activity within the project
 - Join us – information for individuals, organisations and projects on how to get involved
 - What is ARIADNEplus – this leads to the sub-sites that have been translated into several European languages and Japanese
- Activities and Resources – this section includes the existing resources (short reports, deliverables etc.) plus some new outputs from the project.
 - Workshops and seminars – links to two workshop videos, one organised by ARIADNEplus and one jointly with Inception and the European Commission
 - Deliverables – from ARIADNEplus
 - Other publications – outputs such as the ARIADNE Impact booklet, the FAIR Guidelines in various languages and reports
 - ARIADNE Legacy – link to the previous project website content of interest
 - ARIADNE 2014-2018 Deliverables – from the previous project
- Portal – this is the same but is being updated with more data and additional services as planned by the project.
- Training & TNA – this is a new section which has been added to the website following the feedback from the Community Needs Survey. After a soft launch (with the partners), this section was redesigned to reflect the new approach.

[Home](#) [Community](#) [Activities & resources](#) [Portal](#) [Training & TNA](#)

News & events

ARIADNEplus

a data infrastructure serving the archaeological community
worldwide

[LEARN MORE ABOUT THE PROJECT](#)

Integrate and effectively serve a research community that studies the past to better understand the present with the tools and the methodology of the future, in the service of culture and society

Community

ABOUT
ARIADNEPLUS
AND HOW TO
JOIN

Activities and
resources

SHORT
VIDEOS
AND
ACTIVITY
REPORTS

Training & TNA

TRAINING
RESOURCES
FOR
RESEARCHERS

Portal

SEARCH AND
BROWSE
ARCHAEOLOGICAL
DATASETS

News & events

Impact of COVID-19 on Archaeology and Cultural Heritage

The report "Impact of COVID-19 on Archaeology and Cultural Heritage" was written as part of the work undertaken for the deliverable D2.3 Final Report on Community Needs and is available as a separate PDF for [...]

Digital Humanities 2022 – Call for Papers

The 2022 Digital Humanities conference will be held on the 25th-29th July at the Toshi Center Hotel, Tokyo, Japan and also online. The conference Theme is "Responding to Asian Diversity" and the Call for Papers is [...]

Transnational Access Survey for 2022

ARIADNEplus has launched a short survey which aims at verifying if there are researchers interested in participating in Transnational Access (TA) activities as planned in the ARIADNEplus workplan for 2022. Furthermore, the survey seeks to [...]

EAA 2021: ARIADNEplus & SEADDA session presentations available

Session 476: Understanding and expanding capacity in archaeological data management beyond western Europe On the 8th September, ARIADNEplus along with the SEADDA Cost Action hosted a session (476) based on Theme 3: The new normality [...]

Tweets by @ARIADNEp

ARIADNEplus Proj
@ARIADNEplus
Impact of COVID-19 on Archaeology and Cultural Heritage - this report covers academic and preventative archaeology as well as CH institutions such as museums, concluding with implications for the ARIADNEplus project. ariadne-infrastructure.eu/impact-of-covi...

Im...
The
repor
ari...

Nov 5, 2021

ARIADNEplus Project
Retweeted

DH2022
@DH2022_Tokyo
DH2022 CFP is up!
Abstracts are due
November 30th, 2021.
We look forward to

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Web by Prisma Associazione Culturale

Figure 1. The updated Homepage.

The News and Events pages have continued to be updated regularly. Since M18, 13 more events have been posted along with 24 news items and five features.

Associate Partners Home / Associate Partners

Organisations can participate in ARIADNEplus by becoming an Associate Partner. The benefits include access to current research and involvement in the archaeology data community through our network. Associate Partners can increase the visibility of their existing online data through ARIADNE's Portal; no funding is available but support is provided for the aggregation of metadata into the ARIADNE Catalogue.

<p>British Institute at Ankara</p> <p>Egypt</p>	<p>Takin.solutions Ltd.</p> <p>United Kingdom</p>	<p>Monuments Board of the Slovak Republic</p> <p>Slovakia</p>	<p>Data Arc Project</p> <p>International</p>
<p>Directorate for Protection of Cultural Heritage</p> <p>Greece</p>	<p>ROCEEH</p> <p>Germany</p>	<p>Institute of Archaeology in Zagreb</p> <p>Croatia</p>	<p>British School at Athens</p> <p>Greece</p>
<p>University of Minho Archaeology Unit</p> <p>Romania</p>	<p>University of Innsbruck</p> <p>Austria</p>	<p>Department of Information Studies</p> <p>United Kingdom</p>	

Figure 2. The Associate Partners landing page.

The Associate Partners page was recently redesigned as the descriptions and logo for each partner resulted in an increasingly long page as more partners were added. Now the menu link goes to a landing page which shows the geographical coverage and variety of organisations who have joined the project. The Associate Partner name links to its corresponding description in the original page.

Figure 3. The Training Hub Home page.

The Training Hub originally had eight sections. Another section, ‘Other Useful Sources’ was added in M33. Each section links to a separate page with the resources listed with short descriptions, the learning level addressed and the format of the resource. The source is also indicated.

Figure 4. The Depositing datasets in a digital repository set of training resources.

Website Usage Statistics

The website usage is carefully monitored via Google Analytics. The Audience Overview report (Figure 5) provides all the main metrics about the users of the website, as the total volume of visitors, how often they visit and how long they stay.

In the period between M19 to M35 the website has attracted about 10,000 visitors with a total of 28,432 pages viewed. With the exception of the months of August 2020 and 2021 when the number of visitors was slightly lower, there has been a steady rate of visitors, between 500-800 per month, with around 13% being return visitors.

The number of visitors in this reporting period is marginally lower than the previous one, but other website performance indicators continue to be encouraging. Regarding user engagement and retention, all key metrics (pages-per-session, the average session duration and the bounce rate) generally follow the same pattern as identified in the previous reporting period.

Figure 5. Website visitor statistics.

The page/session ratio (Figure 6) shows that the website netted an average of 2.01 pages per visit, the average session duration (Figure 7) is around two minutes, the bounce rate (Figure 8) stands at around 60%, on par with the results recorded in the previous reporting period.

Figure 6. Page/session ratio.

Figure 7. Average session duration.

Figure 8. Bounce rate.

The analysis of the pages viewed (Figure 9) confirms the website’s homepage being the most popular, with 11,788 views. In terms of contents, the pages dedicated to the project’s description (/about-ariadne, /community, /partners, /resources, /associate-partners/, /training-tna) remain in the highest, which is the same as in the previous reporting period. Two new entries appear in the first ten places concerning the project resources (/resources/ariadneplus-deliverables) and the information about the project network (/our-network), confirming that visitors are interested in the output of the project and who is involved through the partners and the network.

Page	Pageviews	% Pageviews
1. /	11,788	41.46%
2. /portal/	3,524	12.39%
3. /about-ariadne/	1,127	3.96%
4. /community/	788	2.77%
5. /partners/	720	2.53%
6. /resources/	609	2.14%
7. /resources/ariadneplus-deliverables/	593	2.09%
8. /associate-partners/	518	1.82%
9. /our-network/	458	1.61%
10. /training-tna/	397	1.40%

Figure 9. Page views.

The Acquisition Overview report (Figure 9) shows the percentage of traffic by source.

Figure 10. Website traffic by source.

‘Direct’ traffic stands at 44.5%, ‘Organic Search’ at 36.6%, ‘Referral’ and ‘Social’ at 14.4% and 4.5% respectively. Compared to the previous period, direct traffic increased while other traffic sources decreased slightly. The reason could be technical. When the referrer field is not communicated by the browser, Analytics is no longer able to catalogue the source of the visit and therefore proceeds ‘by exclusion’, recording it the same way as direct traffic, even if it comes from referral (for example by default a browser that accesses an HTTP site from an HTTPS site does not pass the referrer field for security reasons).

The Referrals diagram (Figure 11) shows the websites that ‘referred’ visitors to the ARIADNEplus website by clicking a link (within another website, for example). The highest number of referral links are from the social networks Twitter (“t.co”) and then from ARIADNE Portal. At position six is Fasti Online, a project of the International Association of Classical Archaeology (AIAC) and the Centre for the Study of Ancient Italy of the University of Texas at Austin (CSAI). At position eight is e-rihs.eu, the Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science which is an important sub-domain for many archaeologists.

Source ?	Acquisition		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?
	1,956 % of Total: 19.56% (10,000)	1,690 % of Total: 17.10% (9,882)	2,815 % of Total: 19.86% (14,174)
1. t.co	359 (17.47%)	281 (16.63%)	556 (19.75%)
2. ariadne-portal.dcu.gr	131 (6.37%)	127 (7.51%)	140 (4.97%)
3. ariadne2.isti.cnr.it	125 (6.08%)	50 (2.96%)	199 (7.07%)
4. archaeologydataservice.ac.uk	97 (4.72%)	83 (4.91%)	116 (4.12%)
5. cultureelerfgoed.nl	66 (3.21%)	65 (3.85%)	75 (2.66%)
6. fastionline.org	60 (2.92%)	52 (3.08%)	66 (2.34%)
7. m.facebook.com	60 (2.92%)	59 (3.49%)	60 (2.13%)
8. e-rihs.eu	53 (2.58%)	49 (2.90%)	60 (2.13%)
9. ics.forth.gr	39 (1.90%)	37 (2.19%)	44 (1.56%)
10. lnec.pt	39 (1.90%)	38 (2.25%)	50 (1.78%)

Figure 11. Referral sources.

3.2.1.1 The individual translated sub-pages ([whatis.ariadne-infrastructure.eu](#))

The individual translated sub-pages are available from [www.whatis.ariadne-infrastructure.eu](#), from the main page is possible to choose the desired language through the corresponding flag.

The Google Analytics Audience Overview report (Figure 12) covers the period from 1st June 2020 to 22nd November 2021.

The sub-site has attracted 2,292 visitors with a total of 5,467 pages viewed. The percentage of returning visitors is around 25%, much higher than the percentage of around 9% recorded in the previous period (1st October 2019 – 31st May 2020), this shows that content was considered interesting by a good percentage of visitors.

Figure 12. Page views for the individual language sub-sites.

The analysis of the most viewed pages (Figure 13) shows that the most visited section remains the one in English, followed by Italian and Greek. The French and Japanese languages also appear in the top ten, considering that Japanese is the last language recently added to the sub-site we can consider this statistic as a signal of user interest in this type of content.

Page ?	Pageviews ? ↓	Unique Pageviews ?	Avg. Time on Page ?
	3,481 % of Total: 63.67% (5,467)	2,338 % of Total: 54.58% (4,284)	00:00:58 Avg for View: 00:00:57 (2.08%)
1. /	2,287 (65.70%)	1,385 (59.24%)	00:00:29
2. /en/	230 (6.61%)	192 (8.21%)	00:01:43
3. /it/	100 (2.87%)	75 (3.21%)	00:01:21
4. /el/	62 (1.78%)	36 (1.54%)	00:03:17
5. /en/researchers/	62 (1.78%)	51 (2.18%)	00:03:40
6. /es/	59 (1.69%)	42 (1.80%)	00:01:47
7. /fr/	56 (1.61%)	48 (2.05%)	00:00:56
8. /en/heritage-managers-and-professionals/	45 (1.29%)	41 (1.75%)	00:02:52
9. /en/citizens/	41 (1.18%)	35 (1.50%)	00:02:30
10. /jp/	34 (0.98%)	21 (0.90%)	00:01:03

Figure 13. The most viewed pages.

3.3 The ARIADNEplus Twitter account

At the end of the ARIADNEplus project, the associated Twitter account @ARIADNE_Network had about 900 followers, with a few additions during the period between the two projects. The ARIADNEplus project used the same Twitter account by modifying the profile reference in @ARIADNEplus, in order to maintain continuity with the old project and to keep the existing followers. The profile was reactivated at the end of January 2019. From the end of January to the end of May 2020, the number of followers grew to 1,727 users at the 1st June 2020. By November 2021, the number of followers had further increased by 162 to 1,889, a 9% increase.

The following table summarises the monthly activity for the ARIADNEplus Twitter account.

Month	No. of Tweets	Views ¹	Profile visitors	Mentions	New followers
Nov-21	1	1821	236	0	5
Oct-21	2	3,013	177	2	16
Sep-21	5	6,640	443	3	3
Aug-21	0	0	168	4	1
Jul-21	1	3,594	533	1	4
Jun-21	1	1,823	286	5	10
May-21	4	5,758	276	1	5
Apr-21	3	6,706	917	13	3
Mar-21	5	11,600	593	13	26
Feb-21	13	13,900	385	9	10
Jan-21	0	0	165	4	2
Dec-20	1	3,716	170	2	3
Nov-20	2	4,995	109	11	9
Oct-20	3	6,280	131	10	12
Sep-20	3	4,969	146	5	15
Aug-20	1	3,756	66	9	12
Jul-20	2	5,901	69	5	7
Jun-20	1	11,100	92	10	13
Total	48	95,572	4,962	107	156
Average	3	5,310	276	6	9

Table 1. Twitter statistics.

Notes

1 – Views include Retweets and mentions (@ARIADNE_Network). These figures will also appear in the Profile visitors and Mentions.

It can be seen that on average, there were three Tweets per month with an average of 5,310 views per month and a gain of nine new followers per month. This level of activity is lower than the first period, reflecting the lack of training and other physical events, but overall the results are positive with an increase in followers, which means all future Twitter campaigns will be reaching a larger audience.

The most popular Tweet during this period was in June 2020, receiving over 8,000 views and 79 clicks on the link:

Interazioni Tweet		×
ARIADNEplus Project @ARIADNEplus Testers wanted by CYI for the main functionalities of the EpHEMERA platform used to visualize online 3D architectural and archaeological models, to extract geometric and morphological information and which will become an ARIADNE service. Survey: https://forms.gle/PPwNM4n55NhUmZBRA ...	Visualizzazioni	8.410
	Interazioni totali	247
	Espansioni dettagli	87
	Clic sul link	79
	Mi piace	37
	Retweet	33
	Clic sul profilo	10
	Risposte	1

Figure 14. Most popular tweet from the last 18 months.

Other tweets concerning the project, such as the presentation given by Julian Richards on how the Portal can be used as a stand-alone research tool, and publication of presentations by ARIADNEplus from conferences such as CAA-GR and CAA-21 usually have between 2,500 to over 3,000 views.

3.4 Slideshare

Several more presentations have been uploaded to the “ariadnenetwork” account following the 2021 CAA and EAA Conferences. These are summarised in the following table which shows the figures recorded at M18 and then at M35. The number of views has more than tripled which is encouraging, and indicates growing engagement in the work of the project.

Sideshare enables promotion of the project to a very wide audience who are looking for specific topics of interest. Viewers may originate from the ARIADNEplus website where the individual links can be embedded in a news item, for example, or can view directly in Slideshare.

Title	Date uploaded	Number of views M18	Number of views M35
Impact of the covid-19 pandemic on archaeological data management in France, The Inrap example	M34		45
From the 2ARCHIS Archaeological Information System to Datarepositórium: Case Study of the Archaeological Coins of Casa Da Bica	M34		47
Archaeological Map of Bulgaria in ARIADNEplus - An Opportunity for Better Post-COVID Times	M34		36
Norwegian Unimus, Nordic Collections, and ARIADNEplus. Encouraging Use and Reuse of Collections, Excavation Documentation and Museum Exhibits	M34		70
EAA 2021 Session 476 Abstracts: Understanding and Expanding Capacity in Archaeological Data Management Beyond Western Europe	M34		34
Ways and Capacity in Archaeological Data Management in Serbia	M34		62
Integrating Archaeological Data from Digital Repositories and Web-based Spatial Databases. IDACORDIG and SUQUIA in Pandemic Times	M34		56
Preserving Historic Building Documentation for Reuse at the National College of Arts, Pakistan	M34		54
Injected by information: a silent (r)evolution in digital archaeology	M34		50
Understanding and Expanding Capacity in Archaeological Data Management Beyond Western Europe	M34		14
DANS-moves into the future	M33		14
Archaeological Linked Data?	M33		15
Digital Infrastructures in Norway	M33		14
MASA Consortium - Round Table	M33		16
Digital Infrastructures and Evolving Technologies in Archaeology (roundtable)	M33		15
'Preferred Formats = Pre-FAIRed Formats' – presentation from FAIR Workshop	M16	56	72
'Archaeological small finds from field to file: Citizen science approach and data-structure of the PAN project' – presentation from FAIR Workshop	M16	26	38

Title	Date uploaded	Number of views M18	Number of views M35
D6.1 Initial report on the Innovation Strategy and Targeted Activities	M15	3	54
ARIADNEplus Community Needs Survey – Key Results	M12	11	52
ARIADNEplus Community Needs Survey (full report)	M12	22	97
Czech Archaeology in the Digital Environment – Digitizing Archaeological agenda In Theory and Practice	M6	48	40
Openarchoe – Semantic web platform for interoperable archaeological data	M6	22	25
ARIADNE at Inrap: Inception, implementation & future	M6	32	39
My data manager is a robot! Mass ingests and migrations & network integrations	M6	32	17
Where is the data?	M6	13	19
Digital Infrastructures for Archaeology: Past, Present and Future Directions	M6	30	66
Total		295	1,061

Table 2. Slideshare statistics

3.5 Promotional materials

Promotional materials were produced for the project during M1 and M2. No further promotional materials have been produced for the second period, there is still stock available but a lack of opportunity to distribute these physically.

3.6 Communication and dissemination activities

Project newsletter

Four issues of the project newsletter were published during Period 1 with five more in Period 2. MailChimp is the tool used to create and distribute the newsletters. The newsletters highlight articles and items from the website with the purpose of allowing recipients clickable access to items of interest to them, whilst also bringing ARIADNEplus to their attention on a regular basis. The Newsletters are distributed via an email list and notices about the newsletter are posted on Twitter. Initially, the Newsletter was distributed to the project participants who are encouraged to forward them to colleagues and other stakeholders. External readers can sign up via the website to be added to the mailing list. The motivation behind publishing a summary version of the newsletter with links to the full articles is to send traffic to the project website. The first newsletter was sent out in May 2019, after the CAA meeting with subsequent ones published on a 3-monthly basis. The campaign statistics are as follows:

Newsletter No.	No. of subscribers	No. of opens	No. of clicks on links
1	156	70 (46.4%)	13 (8.6%)
2	171	79 (46.2%)	23 (13.5%)
3	178	70 (39.8%)	13 (7.4%)
4	183	76 (41.8%)	17 (9.3%)
5	190	77 (40.7%)	15 (7.9%)
6	195	81 (43.3%)	23 (12.3%)
7	205	89 (44.5%)	19 (9.5%)
8	212	91 (43.5%)	11 (5.3%)
9	222	95 (42.8%)	12 (5.5%)

Table 3. Newsletter statistics.

On average, each Newsletter was opened by around 81 people (over 40%) with a click-through rate of around 16%. The current subscriber list stands at 226, an increase of 39 (21%).

Other dissemination materials

A basic set of promotional materials has also been prepared and made available for use. These materials include:

- a set of project logos for use in printed materials and online resources, with branding guidelines and instructions for printers;
- templates for fact sheets, presentations etc.;
- a project description sheet (condensed version from the Grant Agreement, Annex 1 (part A)³
- an ARIADNEplus Essentials PowerPoint presentation.

These materials are made available to members of the project for download from the Intranet of the ARIADNEplus project website. Additional materials will be made available throughout the life of the project as needs are identified by partners.

The planned new project poster has been deferred until the Portal is sufficiently updated with new data and services, and physical events resume.

³ ANNEX 1 (part A) Research and Innovation action 823914 - ARIADNEplus

3.7 Dissemination and communication activities

Events

This Task concerns the planning of regular dissemination and communication at events aimed at increasing awareness about ARIADNEplus, showcasing project achievements and fostering the meeting of the ARIADNEplus community with stakeholders. Events organised by the project are generally co-located with major conferences and symposia, and planned according to favourable opportunities.

For ARIADNEplus, there are two major archaeology conferences, the EAA and the CAA which are of key importance to the project. The EAA, the European Association of Archaeologists annual conference will be where the annual ARIADNEplus General assembly will be held, as many partners will be present for this conference. The EAA represents the main body of European archaeologists, and has had over 11,000 members from 60 countries worldwide working in prehistory, classical, medieval and later archaeology. The EAA also sets professional and ethical standards for archaeological work. CAA (Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology) and CHNT (Cultural Heritage and New Technologies) are organisations for the more digitally inclined archaeologists, each representing smaller communities, but still a main target group for ARIADNEplus activities. According to the dissemination plan, these major archaeology conferences were key platforms for ARIADNEplus, with sessions being hosted at both (virtual) conferences.

In all but three cases, all the events in which ARIADNEplus partners have participated until 1st December 2021 were virtual. In a short pause of the COVID-19 emergency, the project coordinator attended in person an Italian event in presence organized on 14 December 2021 by the Department of Archaeology of the University “L’Orientale” in Naples, Italy, organized also to foster the hope that finally such events will be possible again. Attendance required to comply with all the cautions required by the Italian strict regulations for such events (list of attendees, EU triple vaccination pass controlled at entrance, constantly wearing face masks, hand disinfection, room sanitization, air circulation, etc.). There are some limitations with virtual events which should be noted. Firstly, it is not always possible to know how many people are viewing a specific session – some technologies, such as Zoom, display the total number of participants online at that specific time (some of whom may not be actually be watching) but others do not and the presenters may not always remember to make a note – hence quite a few blanks for the number of people reached. Secondly, there can be technical problems (such as the audience not being able to ask questions or connections dropping) and thirdly, there is a lack of opportunity to mingle and have informal discussions after the session. On the positive side, participation is easier as there are no travel and other costs to be incurred. In total, the partners have taken part in 20 events (25 sessions in total), many with International audiences and hosted not just in Europe but in Japan and Argentina. Where the numbers are known (for approx. 50%), there have been 380 participants (with further views when of presentations and videos have been made available after the events). However, since the two major conferences are among the events where the numbers are missing, it is very likely that the actual numbers are much higher.

Date	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by A+ partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned A+ (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
27-21 July 2020	Human Origins - Digital Future	Heidelberg, Germany - VIRTUAL event	Yes (ROCEEH)	J. Richards (ADS) and F. Niccolucci (PIN)	Yes	Paleo-archaeology and Anthropology		
24-30 Aug 2020	<i>Implementation of a tool for the integration of CENIEH databases with the ARIADNEplus database – 26th EAA Virtual Annual Meeting</i>	Virtual	Yes	Joseba Ríos-Garaizar (CENIEH)	Yes	Archaeologists	Online	
30 Sept 2020	Opening Minds and Digital Collections: Digital Humanities Seminar - https://utlib.ut.ee/en/opening-minds-and-digital-collections-digital-humanities-seminar-30092020	Virtual	RDA Estonia National Event at University of Tartu	Sheena Bassett, PIN	Yes	Digital humanists, librarians, data scientists, historians	30	Dissemination of ARIADNE data management approach to wider humanities audience
18 Nov 2020	ARIADNE session for Freya/ EOSC/SSHOC conference	Virtual	Yes (UoY-ADS)	Julian Richards and Holly Wright (UoY-ADS)	Yes	Information Science	Online	Promotion of ARIADNE to EOSC community

Date	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by A+ partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned A+ (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
25 Nov 2020	RICH-2 Webinar #4: Transnational Access to Social Sciences and Humanities RIs: http://www.rich2020.eu/node/99	Virtual	No - NCP, Polish Academy of Sciences	Sheena Bassett, PIN	Yes	RI TNA Managers	4	Exchange of Best practice re: TNA with SoBigData and Iperion-HS
7 Dec 2020	BSA Upper House Virtual Seminars. Invited lecture on "Excavation archives in 3D: Digital documentation and curation workflows". https://www.bsa.ac.uk/videos/markos-katsianis-excavation-archives-in-3d-digital-documentation-and-curation-workflows/	Athens, Greece	Yes (BSA - British School at Athens: Assoc. Partner)	Markos Katsianis (PP)	Yes	Archaeologists	80 live + 160 views online (2/2021)	Life cycle of 3D GIS archives and data curation issues
Jan 2021	Course on digital archaeology, University of Salamanca	Virtual	No	Alberto Esquivel	No	Archaeologists, students	Approx. 20	
9 Feb 2021	Giving lecture to master students from the VU Amsterdam following the course 'Digital Practice in Archaeology'	Amsterdam The Netherlands	No	Hella Hollander, Valentijn Gilissen	No	Students Archaeology	6	Knowledge exchange about RDM

Date	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by A+ partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned A+ (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
16 Apr 2021	CAA-GR 2021 "Open Digital Archaeological Content in the Connected World: Curation and Stewardship" - https://gr.caa-international.org/2021/07/02/caa-gr2021-sessions-keynote-presentations/	Virtual	No	Holly Wright (ADS), Kate Fernie (CARARE)	Yes	(digital) archaeologists and CH researchers	30	
14-18 June 2021	CAA 2021, ARIADNEplus roundtable: Digital Infrastructures and New (and Evolving) Technologies in Archaeology	Virtual	Yes	Convenors: Holly Wright (ADS), Achille Felicetti (PIN), Ceri Binding (USW)	Yes	(digital) archaeologists and CH researchers		
14-18 June 2021	CAA 2021, Cyprus - https://hypermedia.research.southwales.ac.uk/news/virtually-cyprus/	Virtual	Yes	Ceri Binding (USW) presentation on 'Making Practical Use of Linked Open Data'	Yes	(digital) archaeologists and CH researchers		
14-18 June 2021	CAA 2021, Cyprus - https://hypermedia.research.southwales.ac.uk/news/virtually-cyprus/	Virtual	Yes	Doug Tudhope, panel member on Roundtable (Convenor Isto Huvila), Paradata to the people!	Yes	(digital) archaeologists and CH researchers		
14-18 June 2021	CAA 2021, Cyprus	Virtual	Yes	M. Katsianis (PP), K. Kotsakis (AUTH)	Yes	(digital) archaeologists and CH researchers		

Date	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by A+ partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned A+ (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
22 Jun 2021	Journée d'échanges de pratiques autour des usages du numérique en archéologie (Inrap, Bibracte, Ecoles Française à l'étranger)	Virtual	Yes	Kai Salas Rossenbach Emmanuelle Bryas Inrap	No	Archaeologists, researcher Data manager	60	
2-6 Aug 2021	9 Congreso de Arqueología de la Región Pampeana https://carpa2020.com/	Virtual	No	CONICET (Andrés Izeta)	No	Archaeologists	30	Promotion of Ariadne Plus, FAIRness in archaeological data, Digital heritage
4-6 Aug 2021	XIV Jornadas de Investigadores en Arqueología y Etnohistoria del Centro-oeste del país https://xiv-jornadas-centro-oeste.webnode.com/	Virtual	No	CONICET (Andrés Izeta, Roxana Cattáneo, Isabel Prado, Marcela Tintilay, Ruth Lazarte)	No	Archaeologists	30	Promotion of Ariadne Plus, FAIRness in archaeological data, Digital heritage
6 Sept 2021	The 11th Conference of Japanese Association for Digital Humanities (JADH2021)	Virtual	No	Yuichi Takata, Peter Yanase(NARA)	Yes	Archaeologists, historians, decision makers, Librarians		

Date	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by A+ partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned A+ (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
8 Sept 2021	EAA 2021 Kiel, Aplus session: Understanding and Expanding Capacity in Archaeological Data Management beyond Western Europe	Virtual	Yes	ARUP-CAS, CONICET-IDACOR, INRAP, KHM-UO, NIAM-BAS, Assoc. partners: Institute of Archaeology, Serbia; Univ. Minho	Yes	Archaeologists		
8 Sept 2021	EAA 2021 Kiel, Aplus session: Understanding and Expanding Capacity in Archaeological Data Management beyond Western Europe	Virtual	Yes	CONICET (Andrés Izeta, Roxana Cattáneo)	Yes	Archaeologists		
8 Sept 2021	EAA 2021 Kiel, ARIADNEplus /SEADDA session: Understanding and Expanding Capacity in Archaeological Data Management beyond Western Europe. Presentation: "Archaeological Map of Bulgaria in ARIADNEplus - an opportunity for better post-Covid times"	Virtual	Yes	NIAM-BAS (N. Kecheva, G. Nekhrizov)	Yes	Archaeologists		

Date	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by A+ partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned A+ (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
10 Sept 2021	EAA 2021 Kiel: Presentation: Selecting archaeological archives – an old topic still to be dealt with	Virtual	No	ARUP-CAS (D.Novak), with National Heritage Board of Poland (O.Agnieszka)	Yes	Archaeologists		
21-22 Oct 2021	4th CAA-GR Conference 2020/2021, Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology, Greece. 'Big Data in Archaeology', N.C.S.R. "Demokritos"	Virtual	No	PP (M.Katsianis) with ATHENA (D. Tsifakis)	Yes	(digital) archaeologists and CH researchers		
24 Oct 2021	Measuring Ancient Thrace Project: presentation "AKB in ARIADNEplus" - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T0yx6BTlabE	Virtual	No	NIAM-BAS (N. Kecheva)	No	Archaeologists, historians, decision makers		

Date	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by A+ partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned A+ (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
25-31 Oct 2021	VII Semana de la Arqueología y Paleontología de Buenos Aires https://www.buenosaires.gov.ar/cultura/patrimonio-de-la-ciudad/noticias/vii-semana-de-arqueologia-y-paleontologia-de-buenos-aires	Virtual	No	CONICET (Andrés Izeta, Roxana Cattáneo, Isabel Prado, Marcela Tintilay, Ruth Lazarte)	No	Archaeologists	30	Promotion of Ariadne Plus, FAIRness in archaeological data, Digital heritage
26 Oct 2021	Computer Application in Archaeology XX. CZ 2021; poster: ARIADNEplus: Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Data Networking in Europe	Bořetice (Czech Republic)	No	ARUB-CAS (O. Lečbychová, Z. Kosarová) + ARUP-CAS (D. Novák)	Yes	Archaeologists	70	
14 Dec 2021	Workshop “Il passato incontra il futuro: in che termini?” (The past meets the future: in which terms?)	Naples, Italy	Event co-organized by Associate Partner CISA	Franco Niccolucci (PIN) Andrea D’Andrea (CISA)	No	Archaeologists directors of the Pompeii, Paestum and Herculaneum sites and of the National Archaeological Museum of Naples, MiC	40	Discussion about archaeological data & thesauri and the ARIADNE approach. Booklet printed with interviews including one to F. Niccolucci

Publications

MiBAC-ICCU leads Task 7.4 which concerns the publication of materials by the project including:

- scientific publications in academic journals;
- training materials;
- service specific brochures and fact sheets;
- project brochures and leaflets.

To date, the project has produced the following publications:

Scientific publications in academic journals

Date	Title of Article/Paper	Publication	Authors & organisation	Type of Audience e.g. archaeologists, researchers, data managers etc.	Estimated reach
2020	ARIADNEplus: l'avventura continua	Digitalia, 2-2020, 88-95.	Nicolucci, Franco	Researchers and practitioners in digital archaeology, cultural heritage, and research infrastructures	Several 100
	URL	http://digitalia.sbn.it/article/download/2631/1838			
2020	From Digital Archaeology to Data-Centric Archaeological Research	Magazén, 1(1): 35-53.	Nicolucci, Franco	Researchers and practitioners in digital archaeology, cultural heritage, and research infrastructures	199 views, 48 downloads
	URL	http://doi.org/10.30687/mag//2020/01/002			
2020	An Aegean History and Archaeology Written through Radiocarbon Dates	Journal of Open Archaeology Data 8: 5	Markos Katsianis (PP, GR), Andrew Bevan (UCL, UK), Giorgos Styliaras (PP, GR), Yannis Maniatis (NCSR Demokritos, GR)	Researchers and practitioners in archaeology, prehistory, radiocarbon studies, digital archiving	733 views, 186 downloads, 1 citation
	URL	http://doi.org/10.5334/joad.65			

Date	Title of Article/Paper	Publication	Authors & organisation	Type of Audience e.g. archaeologists, researchers, data managers etc.	Estimated reach
2020	Representing quantitative documentation of 3D cultural heritage artefacts with CIDOC CRMdig.	International Journal on Digital Libraries, 21: 359–373.	Catalano, C.E., Vassallo, V., Hermon, S. et al.	Researchers and practitioners in digital archaeology, cultural heritage, and research infrastructures	226 Accesses, 1 Citations
	URL	https://doi.org/10.1007/s00799-020-00287-3			
2020	File Formats for the Long-term Digital Storage of Cultural Heritage Data, pp.71-76	Recording and Utilization of Cultural Property Information via Digital Technologies Vol. 2 Open Science, Data Preservation, Intellectual Property	Yuichi Takata (NARA)	Researchers and practitioners in digital archaeology, cultural heritage, and research infrastructures	Views 5,143 Downloads 3,358
	URL	https://doi.org/10.24484/sitereports.69974			
2021	Documentation of Archaeology-Specific Workflow for Airborne LiDAR Data Processing	Geosciences 11 (1), 26	Lozić, E., Štular, B.	Researchers and practitioners in digital archaeology, cultural heritage, and research infrastructures	Views 1,388 Citations 5
	URL	http://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences11010026			
2021	Reconfiguring the 3D excavation archive. Technological shift and data remix in the archaeological project of Paliambela Kolindros, Greece	Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports, Vol.36, 102857	Katsianis, M., Kotsakis, K., Stefanou, F.	Researchers and practitioners in digital archaeology, cultural heritage, and research infrastructures	Views 17
	URL	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2021.102857			

Date	Title of Article/Paper	Publication	Authors & organisation	Type of Audience e.g. archaeologists, researchers, data managers etc.	Estimated reach
2021	Heterogeneous Document Embeddings for Cross-Lingual Text Classification	36th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing (SAC'21), Virtual Event, Republic of Korea, 22-26 March 2021	Moreo, A., Pedrotti, A., Sebastiani, F.	Researchers in machine learning and NLP	Views 61 Downloads 49
	URL	https://zenodo.org/record/4467989			
2021	Assessing Visual Perception in Heritage Sites with Visual Acuity: Case study of the Cathedral of St. John the Theologian in Nicosia, Cyprus	Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage, 14(1), Article 1	Polig, M., Papacharalambous, D.G., Bakirtzis, N., Hermon, S.	Researchers and practitioners in digital cultural heritage and archaeology	Downloads 209 Citations 1
	URL	https://doi.org/10.1145/3417710			
2021	Adding Japanese Periods to PeriodO	Recording and Utilization of Cultural Property Information via Digital Technologies Vol. 3 Copyright, Cultural Resource Videos, GIS, 3D Data, Online Publishing	Mikiharu Takeuchi (NARA)	Researchers and practitioners in digital archaeology, cultural heritage, and research infrastructures	Views 1,765 Downloads 1,140
	URL	http://doi.org/10.24484/sitereports.90271			
2021	Form, Content, and Space: Methodological Challenges in the Study of Medieval and Early Modern European Graffiti.	Papers from the Institute of Archaeology, 2021, 30(1): pp. 1–25.	Trentin, M. G. (CYI)	Researchers and practitioners in digital archaeology, cultural heritage, and research infrastructures	Published 15/11/201 Views 75 Downloads 8
	URL	https://doi.org/10.14324/111.444.2041-9015.1283			

The PARTHENOS Guidelines to “FAIRify data management and make data reusable” have been translated into more languages by ARIADNEplus, including Czech (391 views and 255 downloads), Portuguese (477 views, 327 downloads) and Turkish (551 views, 358 downloads) during Period 2 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3937149>).

3.8 National Campaigns for the Portal

During the first two years of the ARIADNEplus project, the activities focussed on the preparation of a new, improved inclusive data model which can accommodate datasets from many new archaeological sub-domains which require specific vocabularies and specialised data models (called Application Profiles). Examples include Ancient DNA (aDNA) and Heritage Science. Moreover, the new Portal caters for individual data records as well as collections. Consequently, the remapping of existing datasets and the addition of new ones has seen the first datasets being uploaded into the Portal during Period 2 onwards. Many of the collections of datasets have come from national providers so it was agreed that the best approach at this stage (whilst the Portal itself is being updated) would be for each provider to carry out a national dissemination campaign (mainly via social media) to encourage their archaeological community members to visit the Portal and explore their datasets along with those already existing within the Portal. This approach ensured the Portal Infrastructure would have a growing number of visitors without there being a sudden massive increase (which could potentially cause performance problems) and that matching the newly available data to visitors would not lead to disappointment, putting off future users.

The national campaigns started in M27 with ADS, who ran a week-long Twitter campaign, blogged and also had an article published on a key UK website popular with archaeologists, the British Archaeological Jobs Resource (BAJR). Slovenia (ZRC-SAZU) followed around 3 weeks later and Bulgaria (NAIM-BAS) another 3 weeks after that in M28, both also choosing Twitter to promote examples of their datasets. After this, the next dataset to be uploaded was in M33 by ROCEEH who are based in Germany (but the datasets are geographically related to Africa). They also conducted their own dissemination campaign but their user base is more widely geographically spread.

The statistics for the new Portal start from January 2021 which is when the upgraded version was implemented with the enhanced search facilities following in early February when the Portal became available to the public. This was announced to the ARIADNE Community, which probably accounts for the initial increase in visitors at this time. ADS launched their week-long Twitter campaign (along with the other channels) on the 15th March which directly correlates to a large increase in visitors from the UK at this time.

Visitors to the Portal

From 1st January 2021 to 27th November 2021, there were a total of 7,165 visitors to the Portal. Some of the obvious spikes in visitor numbers directly correlate to national campaigns and there is also a noticeable spike in visits in M33 after the ROCEEH campaign. Users during the spike periods mostly come via referrals which also indicate that this is a result of the social media campaigns, as most visitors otherwise arrive via organic search.

The countries who have promoted the Portal, i.e. the UK, Slovenia and Bulgaria, when their data has been uploaded, have seen a large uplift in visitor numbers over the following weeks.

Country	Campaign dates	Total No. Visitors before campaign	Total No. Visitors 14 days after campaign	% Increase
UK	15-19 March 2021	172	243	141%
Bulgaria	15 April onwards	86	16	19%
Slovenia	31 March – 2 April	3	8	267%

Note that Slovenia has a relatively small population (approx. 2m) and their visitor numbers increased from 3 to 8 two weeks after their campaign and as of the 31st May stands at 14 users, which is nearly five times as many. Bulgaria gained another 20 users during May. This seems to suggest that the dissemination causes an initial surge followed by a smaller wave of visitors.

At M35, the UK is responsible for 57% of visitors with Bulgaria in 4th place with 4%. Slovenia provides 0.3% of the total visitors.

3.9 Transnational Access and Training

Transnational access

Transnational access (TNA) provides focussed training, predominantly for young researchers, and is often their first experience working with a research infrastructure. There are three providers in ARIADNEplus who offer TNA as follows:

- PIN VASTLab offers one-week, in-house training courses tailored to single or groups of users who need to develop their archaeological datasets and improve their interoperability, using standards such as CIDOC-CRM and the infrastructure tools and services;
- UoY-ADS, as an accredited archaeological data repository, specialise in data management and stewardship and offer in-house visits, usually of around three days, to users needing guidance and support with this topic;
- CNR-ISTI is devoted to ICT research and provides expertise in the design of archaeological datasets and thesauri. In-house visits are offered to users requiring support with the creation, access and integration of such datasets with full access to facilities such as computers and tools. The VCL laboratory specialises in 3D data acquisition and management and offers in-house training with full use of its visual media tools. This type of training is offered as a five-day summer school.

The first call, for in-house training at PIN and ADS, resulted in 16 applicants of which 13 received offers. Of these, three students were able to complete their training at PIN and ADS prior to the COVID-19 travel restrictions but the remaining candidates have had their training places held until it is possible to travel once again. The planned Summer Schools at CNR were cancelled, and no further calls were made during period 2 due to the ongoing COVID restrictions. PIN is currently conducting a survey to determine the demand for TNA, should it be possible to go ahead in 2022, and the preferred format in order to find out what it will be possible to offer next year.

One positive outcome to report is that Mia Trentin from CYI managed to attend her TNA training on CIDOC-CRM at PIN and has just published a paper which uses the knowledge gained from her TNA visit. The paper is *Form, Content, and Space: Methodological Challenges in the Study of Medieval and Early Modern European Graffiti*. Papers from the Institute of Archaeology, 2021, 30(1): pp. 1–25. As mentioned previously in section 3.7.2.

Training

Activities under this task concern the planning of short training events, usually organised during important events for potential users of the ARIADNEplus services. They may consist of generic tutorials or short, hands-on demonstrations of individual services. They also create good promotional opportunities to advertise the use of ARIADNEplus services. The task also includes planning the creation of training webinars or video tutorials for publication on the web site, possibly adapting existing training material. This training task will complement the training activity produced by TNA, which will be based on individual participation for a longer duration. ZRC SAZU is in charge of planning the training; PIN(PRISMA) will manage the technical production of webinars or video tutorials; all partners will be involved as possible trainers, or as training event organisers.

No further training events have been organised by the project during period two. Another workshop on FAIR Data Management is planned for the final period in 2022 and discussions are in progress as part of WP2 for workshops and training targeted at Heritage Managers and archaeologists in the CEE

areas that are not represented, although the project has acquired a number of Associate Partners who are improving the coverage in this area.

The Training Hub, launched in Period 1, has continued to grow with the addition of some new modules, such as the Guide for Archaeological Data Management Planning under the section “Defining and implementing a Data Management Plan (DMP)”, and a new section, “Other Useful Sources” following a recommendation from the Technical Review.

3.10 Monitoring and assessment

The dissemination programme is monitored and assessed to review:

- what messages (communication of benefits) are going out and who is seeing them;
- whether those messages are being understood and remembered;
- whether the messages are influencing opinions, attitudes and behaviours.

This information will help in planning subsequent phases of the marketing strategy, in developing future marketing activities and in order to make revisions of this marketing strategy plan. It will ensure the marketing strategy is effectively reaching the target audiences and they are acting on the messages they receive.

Success indicators:

- stakeholder involvement;
- number of institutional stakeholders involved e.g. by becoming associates, participating in bilateral meetings, sending researchers to participate in TNA and training events, taking part in user surveys and other activities;
- user involvement;
- number of users participating in project training activities, attending workshops and presentations etc.;
- project website developed;
- number of unique visitors;
- research infrastructure online services;
- number of unique users;
- number of ARIADNEplus Twitter followers, reach (number of people who see messages and retweets);
- number of people reached via other media channels e.g. newspapers, YouTube, interviews;
- number of presentations at relevant conferences and events;
- number of presentations and project publications downloaded from Slideshare;
- number of readers of ARIADNEplus email newsletter.

The following figures have been produced by looking at the numbers achieved by ARIADNE as reported in the final Dissemination report⁴, which were used as guidelines to obtain realistic targets.

⁴ D4.7 Final Dissemination Report – ARIADNE Project No. 313193

Description	Measure	Month 36 Target	Month 35 Actual	Comments
Stakeholder involvement	Number of institutions	100	>160	Survey (150) + Associate Partners 11
User involvement	Number of participants	5,000	>5,000	E.g. 700 survey respondents, 3000+ Twitter views, 800+ reached via events, journals
Project website	Visitors	20,000	20,578	Google Analytics figure 01/02/2019-28/11/2021
Research infrastructure online services (Portal)	Anonymous users	7,500	7,165	Since January 2021
Social networks (Twitter)	Number of members	1,800	1,889	Nov 2021
Social networks (Twitter)	Number of people reached	10,000	>8,000	Max. is 8,410 for a single tweet
Communication via other channels	Number of people reached	3,000	>10,000	Papers views – 9,950, FARIFY Guidelines 1,419 views, Slideshare 1,061 views
Presentations at international events	Number of people reached	200	>500	Total audience = 380 for 50% of events
Downloads from Slideshare*	Number of people reached	1,000	1,061 views.	Download rate about 1% of views
Newsletters	Number of readers	150	~95 actual readers per edition.	222 subscribers, Approx. 43% opened

Table 4: Indicators to be used for monitoring the dissemination impact.

At M36, most of the indicator targets have been met and/or exceeded. The Slideshare download figures are on the low side, however the view figure exceeds the target. The ARIADNE Impact publication is not available on Slideshare but via Zenodo (so that it can be assigned a DOI). Since the latter has been downloaded 1,409 times to date from Zenodo, the two figures combined easily exceed

the target of 1,000. The newsletter target has also been missed in terms of readers (but not subscribers) but an open rate of 43% is very good, so this is an effective communication channel.

In conclusion, the indicators show that during the second period, ARIADNEplus has continued to be effective at building its community and disseminating information about the project. Promotion of the key output, the updated Portal, has only begun earlier this year but is building steadily.

3.11 Recommendations from the Strategic Advisory Board concerning Dissemination and Communication

A number of recommendations were made by the Strategic Advisory Board regarding WP7, which were included in the first report (Appendix 1). Many of which have already been taken on board and at M36, the current status is as follows.

Dissemination

- Network with as many other similar projects with the ARIADNEplus website.
 - This recommendation has been implemented and is based around the Community section. Networking with other projects has taken place through meetings and events and our associated members and allies such as SEADDA are highlighted.
- Besides creating own channels, ARIADNEplus should exploit existing local projects to improve public dissemination. Among others, the following were mentioned:
 - Heritage Information Access Strategy by Historic England, Local Authority Historic Environment Records in England;
 - several liaisons of this type are described in D2.3 Interim Report on Networking and Integration.
- Printed materials continue to be a useful means to broadcast project results. Leaflets or other materials that can be taken away by conference attendees would magnify the project's resonance within the community.
 - leaflets as described in section 3.6.2 were designed for this purpose. However, very few opportunities to use printed materials at present.
- Print-on-demand: Archaeolingua continues to publish, for example, the EAC's Annual Meetings Extended Abstracts with links to the full online versions of the papers. Libraries and archives request the published paper copies, which are kept for consultation;
 - Archeolingua published the book "The ARIADNE Impact" in 2019 following the successful session at CAA, Krakow.
- Webinars: some of the presentations given during the ARIADNEplus kick-off were excellent and could easily be converted into webinars.
 - New Workshop and seminars section on the website has two webinars published. Some short videos are planned for the final period when all the tools and services will be available.
- Media coverage is an aspect that has not been fully developed. Appointing a media expert to follow the project and interact with the media (television, radio, newspapers, and so on) would be of great advantage.
 - Some coverage has also taken place, e.g. NARA.
- Museums: at this stage, the project is involved only with a few museums that have a research section. One of the project's implementation pilots is led by the Moesgaard Museum (MOMU) in Denmark. The pilot can be disseminated through NEMO, the Network of European Museum Organisations.
 - To be organised when the pilot is ready during Period 3.

Conferences

- There are many new fields of research (Bio-Archaeology, aDNA, Environmental Studies, and so on) that are unaware of the ARIADNEplus project. The project must therefore increase its presence in specialised conferences/events with the aim of reaching these different academic communities.
 - BSA Upper House Virtual Seminars. Invited lecture on "Excavation archives in 3D: Digital documentation and curation workflows", Dec 2020
 - Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology, Greece. 'Big Data in Archaeology', Oct 2021".
 - At present, we are building up a contacts database, part of which is focussing on the 13 specialist areas covered by the project in order to send out targeted communications.
- The EAC Annual Symposium is another venue to gain the governmental perspective on the work of ARIADNEplus. It was recommended to have another symposium, such as the one that took place in Brighton in 2016; this will be looked at for Period 3, once the Portal is ready – depends on theme.
- The project needs to be more present at events where computer scientists are involved. This audience is not fully aware of the problems related to the integration of archaeological research, and vice-versa.

Other means of addressing this issue are in development. These include:

 - Publication of reports by the sub-domain groups;
 - Preparation of training materials which will cover this issue;
 - Guest feature on website to illustrate this.

In summary, the project has already adopted many of the recommendations and will address the remaining suggestions plus any new recommendations from the SAB as it progresses.

4 Communication and dissemination plan for M37-M48

The Communication and Dissemination activities will continue to use the website, workshops and conference sessions, social media (i.e. Twitter, Slideshare, Facebook etc.) to promote the ARIADNE infrastructure to all of its stakeholders and beyond. As the work of the project progresses and the outputs start to crystallise, it will be possible to start focussing on specific archaeological sub-domains as mappings and vocabularies are completed by WP4. Some specific activities that are planned for period 3, and which take account of the current situation, are described in this section.

4.1 The Training Hub

The Community Needs Survey⁵ asked respondents about their training needs for a number of identified topics. The responses resulted in the Training Hub, a collection of curated resources, in nine sections covering a range of topics as follows:

1. Applying open/Fair Principles to archaeology
2. Depositing project datasets in a digital repository
3. Data science skills
4. Managing datasets from large archaeological projects
5. Managing a digital repository of archaeological data
6. Metadata and vocabularies for archaeological datasets
7. Defining and implementing a Data Management Plan (DMP)
8. Working with Research Infrastructures
9. Other useful sources

The Hub will be expanded during Period 3 to include a new section containing training materials directly relating to the Portal and Services. The first of these resources is being planned as part of the activities of WP2 which aims to promote ARIADNE to Heritage Managers in parts of CEE not covered by the current partners (although some of the Associate Partners do) and will provide a simple guide that explains what an organisation needs to do to supply its data to the Portal. Other materials planned will cover how to use the search facility for the Portal and also address the services such as the Lab VRE and the Geo-services.

ARIADNEplus has also planned to provide some training in the form of internal workshops for its participants plus two Workshops on the FAIR Data Principles in Years 2 (completed) and 4 (in planning).

4.2 Printed material & templates

Assuming that physical events will return in the final year, a poster will be produced to highlight the outputs from the project such as the new data, tools and services developed for the Portal, the Training Hub, etc. Other activities planned (for Task 7.4) are:

1. A project summary leaflet ready for both download and print. Partners can produce their own language versions (either send text to MIBACT-ICCU for typesetting or can get this done

⁵ D2.1 Initial Report on Community Needs, October 2019

themselves with original files, Adobe InDesign). Print versions will be done if physical meetings go ahead during the next period.

2. A booklet to promote the Network and Portal, as was successfully produced for the original project. Deadline November 2022 for Final Event.
3. Communication targeted towards specific communities. Around 14 specific sub-groups are identified in WP4 - we will work with these groups to:
 - Identify the key communication channels and organisations for each speciality (websites, blogs, journals and publications, Twitter feeds, FB groups etc.) and who will be responsible for contacting them (some partners may be better placed or prefer to do this themselves, especially if sending translations).
 - Prepare tailored texts (with graphics) for each sub-group which highlight how ARIADNEplus benefits their specialism for dissemination. This may include an application profile, what datasets are available within the Portal, benefits of being part of the network, etc. These can be translated for national dissemination by partners and adapted for use as needed. It should be possible to start with an outline which can then be reviewed and updated by each group as required.

4.3 Publications and internal reports

The Project Newsletter will continue to be published every three months with a view to increasing its circulation and reach via the Community pages.

Within the project (as part of the work in WP4, Task 4), several sub-domains have been identified who are currently working on their specific vocabularies and mappings (as part of the AO-CAT):

- Paleo-anthropology
- Bio-archaeology and Ancient DNA
- Environmental Archaeology
- Inorganic materials study
- Dating
- Field Survey
- Archaeological finds made by general public
- Remote Sensing
- Standing Structures
- Spatio-temporal data
- Maritime and underwater archaeology
- Archaeological fieldwork
- Inscriptions
- Burials.

As part of this work in progress, the partners involved produce short reports which are of interest to their colleagues and peers as well as the wider community. The first of these internal reports, addressing Spatio-temporal data, has just been released and an edited version, (to comply with GDPR), will be published shortly and circulated to the ARIADNEplus Community. Further reports are due in Period 3 which will provide a comprehensive overview of the many different types of archaeology disciplines involved in the project and the challenges and solutions that each has decided upon.

4.4 Events

The main events for archaeologists during the final period (M37-M48) continue to be Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (CAA) and the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA). In addition, DH2022, Tokyo is also being targeted as this will be an excellent opportunity for promotion of the project on Asia. The European Archaeology Council Symposium (EAC) is another possibility, depending on the theme.

These conferences will take place during Period 3 and participation is planned as follows:

- 28th EAA Annual Meeting in Budapest, Hungary, 31 August - 3 September 2022
 - A session proposal around the topic of data reuse in archaeology has been accepted, and will provide an opportunity to present not only the Portal and its possibilities, but (ideally) also use cases for different sub-fields of archaeology and digital skills levels.
 - If attendance in person is feasible, the project will also have a booth to promote the Portal and project (ARIADNE Community).
- DH2022, Tokyo 25 – 29 July 2022
 - The abstract for a short paper, “Integrating the Japanese Archaeological Dataset into the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure”, is in the process of being finalised for submission and, if accepted, will be presented by NARA and PIN.
- CAA 2022 – Oxford, UK 8-11 August. The dates just been announced, options for participation will be explored.
- EAC Annual Symposium - to be announced.

ARIADNEplus completes in December 2022 and a Final Project Event is scheduled to showcase the Portal and results of the project. As it is unclear exactly what the format will be, as formal planning for this has not yet started.

In addition, partners will be encouraged to participate in events relating to many new fields of research (Bio-Archaeology, DNA, Environmental Studies etc.) and also those attended by computer scientists to disseminate the ARIADNE Infrastructure.

Finally, the WP7 team will continue encourage and support partners who wish to organise their own project-related regional/national events.

5 Conclusion

Periods 1 and 2 have focussed on disseminating the project and its initial results to the more immediate stakeholder community of researchers and academics, achieving the majority of the targets. In the final Period, dissemination and communication will widen to reach a larger audience, driven by many more datasets being uploaded into the Portal, the search facilities being finalised, and a raft of new services aimed at enabling researchers to work across boundaries, time zones and disciplines. Dissemination will also become more focussed, tailoring information and messages to reach specific sub-domains and producing training materials to promote wide usage of the ARIADNEplus offerings. Working hand in hand with WP2, WP7 will continue to build the ARIADNE Community to ensure the future sustainability of the Data Infrastructure.